

Action Research

Poster presentation: Presentation of Art Work, Artist statement, and Research Report Content

Title: Ipad, I-play & I-consent

Research aims and questions: This research is aimed to improve my practice around the use of Information Technology in my early childhood center. How can I improve my practice around the use of Information Technology in my early childhood center?

Reconnaissance stage:

- investigated the current use of IT tools like tablets and iPad with children aged 1-2.5 years. To investigate MY practice.
- Literature (Pohio, 2009) informs about different opinions on the use of IT in teaching with 60% positive effects and 40% negative effects considering a supervised use of technology. Focus on screen time, behavioral issues, and attention span issues that come along with it.
- Room observation: Children were glued to the screen, and short-tempered when iPad was taken away. minimal to no interactions, continuous watching, and only about 40% interact with videos

Intervention stage:

- intervened by discussing with the team about the impact of IT use on cognitive behavior in children. 90% agreed with the negative impacts.
- The intervention plan included more interaction-based resources for children rather than screen-watching tasks. interaction using music, videos, dance, and yoga with instructional videos, 'how to do videos on plant life and the life cycle of animals, activities in nature, and more puppet-based stories.
- Realized the importance and impact of consent during the intervention. 75% of children engaged in choices and decision-making of their own play, choosing their content and choosing HOW they want to interact, CONSENT was hugely part of the intervention plan.

Evaluation Stage:

- Consent was the key, children were more confident about their choices regarding what they wanted to do, and how they want to do it. The POWER to decide gave children meaningful learning experiences with a noticeable increase in participation, communication, interactions with each other, and off-screen learning.
- significance of interaction-based activities had a direct result on performance and play was observed with increased memory skills, vocabulary learning, and 2 syllable phrases used by toddlers.
- by the end of action research, better peer relationships, better teacher-child relationships, and increased interactions were observed as compared to continuous screen time resulting in short tempers in the beginning.

Research significance: During the reconnaissance phase, it was observed that a lot of children did not participate or interact with digitally interactive tasks. As a result, the CONSENT of children was made a priority. Children are given choices about when to interact, with what to interact, and how to bring videos to real life, in play. Found the significance of interaction, and value of NO. increase in child participation, increase in group play and mat times, increased connection with children and teachers, the value of own consent.

As a teacher, I feel confident about my practice of using IT tools with children. There are a few things that were significant to me and indeed added to my learning after the whole action research project. They were: Impact of digital tools depending on the way a kaiako uses them with children (Pohio, 2009, mentions that the impact of IT on young children depends on the role of adults/teachers present during these experiences); the importance of having digital tools with children as they are part of a growing technological environment and should be aware of the purpose, use, and features of these IT tools (Herodotou (2018) noted beneficial consequences on the development of literacy, as well as beneficial effects on math, science, problem-solving, and self-efficacy; the significance of interaction with the screen and play - learning about environment by watching and doing; the value of 'NO' - consenting children on their learning, choices to participate, choices on different ways of participation and

choices on what content to interact with; and finally, connection with children resulting from meaningful experiences rather than ‘watching’ a video (Brown, 2007). This has also guided my ethical practices of being a consenting, respectful, and privacy-concerned kaiako, and significantly given me a wider understanding of children’s learning.

Implications for the future: It is recommended to have more professional development courses on IT use with different age groups. It is also suggested that my practice can be widened into multi-lingual and multi-cultural aspects, research on different practices worldwide as well as teaching practices that support children with additional needs and linguistic support can be worked on. This can also be extended into transition support for new tamariki and transition planning into school.

References:

- Brown, M. (2007). *A question to ponder: Should teachers drive or be driven by technology?* *Computers in New Zealand Schools*, 19(3), 2-3.
- Herodotou, C. (2018). Young Children and Tablets: A Systematic Review of Effects on Learning and Development. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 34(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12220>
- Pohio, L. (2009). *The implementation and integration of information and communication technologies in early childhood education: Teachers’ perspectives*. Unpublished thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the degree of Master of Education, Unitec Institute of Technology, New Zealand.

Research aim and question

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How can I improve my practice around the use of Information Technology in my early childhood centre?

Ipad, I-play & I-consent

During reconnaissance phase, it was observed that a lot of children did not participate or interact with digitally interactive tasks

As a result, the CONSENT of children was made a priority. Children are given choices when to interact, with what to interact, and how to bring videos to real life, in play

Found the significance of interaction, and value of NO. increase in child participation, increase in group play and mat times. increased connection with children and teachers, the value of own consent

Reconnaissance stage

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Different ways children interact with technology: children staring at the screen vs children choosing to do yoga with a video on iPad displayed further

We intervened (Intervention stage)

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"Tell me and I forget. Teach me and I remember.
Involve me and I learn".

Research significance

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